

*Launch of the participatory, artistic research project
THIS LAND IS NOT MINE by Kat Austen*

*21.9.2020 Launch of the Online-Database Sounds of Lusatia
26.9.2020 Workshop - Open Lab at Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum für
moderne Kunst (BLMK)*

‘This Land is Not Mine’ is an participatory artistic research project by Kat Austen that opens a dialogue about current socio-economic structural changes in the multicultural region. Sounds of Lusatia are collected in collaboration with the population through workshops and via a specially-developed crowdsourced online database, launching on the 21st September 2020. Special attention in the project is paid to the importance and role of the Sorbs in framing the culture of the region. Together with Lusatians, Austen researches the continued transformation of regional identity in an area undergoing a profound transition due to the ongoing move away from the lignite mining industry that for so long has dominated the land’s narrative.

In 2021 an exhibition project will take place at the Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum für moderne Kunst (BLMK).

‘This Land is Not Mine’ focusses on how identity plays a role in shaping the sustainability of the region in the future, with a particular focus on integrating Sorbian identity in a coherent narrative for the region’s population. Sustainability requires not only this stepping away from coal and innovation, but also to connect with less tangible resources already present, such as culture, experience and tradition.

UPCOMING EVENTS

I.

LAUNCH Website <https://lausitzklang.katausten.com>

Sounds of Lusatia | Online Sound database

Monday, 21st September 2020

Contribution to the database is freely accessible to anyone who wants to take part in the project. You can choose between German, English and Sorbian. The collected audio files can be uploaded independently in the formats wav, mp3, mp4 and ogg.

II.

**Workshop - Open Lab at Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum für moderne Kunst Cottbus
Wasserklang Open Lab Synopsis, 26st September 2020**

Dr Austen explores the human relationship with water using artistic research techniques that meld together embodied explorations with those mediated by sensing equipment. Led and facilitated by Dr Austen, this workshop introduces participants to two of these artistic research methods that make use of scientific equipment and embodied techniques to connect with water, and facilitates the exploration of local water using these methods.

General Information

Where? Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum für moderne Kunst (BLMK)
Dieselkraftwerk, Uferstraße/Am Amtsteich 15, 03046 Cottbus, Event space

When? 26th September 2020, 11:00 - 5:30 pm

Participants: max. 6 per Round

Registration is recommended. In the case of free spots spontaneous participation without a pre-registration is possible. The participation is free of charge.

Registration via email kunstvermittlung.cottbus@blmk.de or +49 355 49494040

Structure

Round I

11:00 - 11:45 Introduction to theory and methods (45 minutes)

Dr Austen introduces the overarching artistic research practice, and outlines the theory behind chemical sensing of water, and embodied exploration of the non-human other using sound based techniques.

11:45 - 12:30 Listening to the water and discussion - sample collection and exploration (45 minutes)

Workshop participants will explore a nearby body of water, collecting water and audio samples using hydrophones.

// Lunch break

Round II

13:30 - 14:15 Introduction to theory and methods (45 minutes)

14:15 - 15:00 Listening to the water and discussion - sample collection and exploration (45 minutes)

// Break

Round III

15:30 - 16:15 Introduction to theory and methods (45 minutes)

16:15 - 17:00 Listening to the water and discussion - sample collection and exploration (45 minutes)

ARTIST STATEMENT

In her project 'This Land is not Mine', Kat Austen explores the diverse identities of Lusatia. Austen invites Lusatians to collaborate in this artistic research, which focusses on changes in the region and relationships between humans, landscape, water and ecosystems. This collaboration forms the foundation of a multimedia work, which will be a synthesis of artistic research and the artists' individual impressions. 'This Land is not Mine' is an independent artistic research project that has no connections to regional or supra-regional political parties or actors.

We are happy to answer any further questions you may have about the objectives and content of the project. Please use the options below to contact us.

ABOUT KAT AUSTEN

Kat Austen is a person. In her artistic practice, she focusses on environmental issues. She melds disciplines and media, creating sculptural and new media installations, performances and participatory work. Austen's practice is underpinned by extensive research and theory, and driven by a motivation to explore how to move towards a more socially and environmentally just future.

Working from her studio in Berlin, Austen is currently Artist in Residence at WRO Art Center through the EMAP/EMARE programme, Artistic Fellow at IASS Potsdam, Associate at ZeM, Brandenburg, Artist in Residence at the Faculty of Maths and Physical Sciences, University College London and Senior Teaching Fellow at UCL Arts and Sciences. She is a Fellow of the Royal Society of Arts, a member of the bbk, an inaugural member of the London Creative Network and is co-founder of the DIY Hack the Panke collective in Berlin.

Austen's field research has included a voyage around the Canadian High Arctic as Artist in the Arctic 2017 for Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute (University of Cambridge) for her project The Matter of the Soul. In 2018 Austen was selected as inaugural Cultural Fellow in Art and Science at the Cultural Institute, University of Leeds for the same project. Austen has been awarded residencies internationally, including with NYU Shanghai, ArtOxygen Mumbai, LAsTheatre, the Clipperton Project and Utter! Spoken word.

Austen has exhibited at Bonhams Art Gallery, London; The Polar Museum, Cambridge; Kuehlhaus, Berlin, among others, and her work is held internationally in private collections. She has performed around the globe, including at Opera North, Leeds; Fusion Festival, Berlin and Headlands Center for the Arts, San Francisco.

Workshop Registration

Brandenburgisches Landesmuseum
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CONTACT

Project related questions

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